

Solvent Extraction Studies on Thiocyanate Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

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The extraction behaviour of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) thiocyanate complexes has been studied in some oxygenated solvents, high molecular weight amines, tributyl phosphate and pyridine. The effect of different variables on extraction has been investigated. The extracting species have been identified using loading ratio data and by the method of slope analysis. On the basis of extraction data some mutual separations and separations from other commonly associated elements have been carried out. Relative merits and limitations of different extraction systems are discussed.

THE thiocyanate ion is a well known ligand and forms complexes with numerous metal ions which are usually stoichiometrically analogous to the corresponding halo complexes. In view of its strong complexing nature this ion has been widely employed in various areas of chemical analysis including solvent extraction of metal ions¹. Earlier reports indicate that a large number of investigations have been carried out on the extraction of metal thiocyanate complexes in different extraction systems. However, not much work^{1,2} was reported on the extraction of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) as thiocyanates. The separations involving cadmium and mercury are of particular interest to environmentalists as the two elements are serious pollutants of the biosphere.

Studies were initiated in this laboratory sometimes back on the extraction of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) thiocyanate complexes in some oxygenated solvents³, high molecular weight amines (HMWA)⁴⁻⁷ and in non-polar solvents in the presence of neutral donors like tri-*n*-butyl phosphate⁸ and pyridine⁹. These investigations mainly dealt with the studies on the mechanism of extraction and utilized the extraction data for obtaining some typical separations of metal ions.

The present paper summarizes the results of these investigations on the extraction of thiocyanate complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II). The extracting species have been mainly identified by the method of slope analysis. However, in the case of extractions in high molecular weight amines, the extracting species have also been identified by extraction isotherms and analysis of the organic extract at the maximum loading conditions. In Hg(II)-thiocyanate neutral ligand systems, the species could not be identified because of nonconclusive results. The extraction behaviour of some other commonly associated elements has also been studied under identical conditions and based on the extraction data some mutual binary separations have been proposed. Attempts have been made to compare the efficiency of different systems for attaining metal ion separations involving Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II).

Experimental

All inorganic chemicals and organic solvents used were of analytical grade. Primene JM-T and Amberlite LA-1 (Rohm and Haas Co., U.S.A.) and Alamine 336 and Aliquat 336 (General Mills, Inc., U.S.A.) were all practical grade materials and used without further purification. The metal ion solutions were generally prepared from sulphate salts and standardised by standard methods. ⁵⁴Mn, ⁵⁸Co, ⁶⁵Zn, ^{110m}Ag, ^{114m}In, ^{115m}Cd, ²⁰³Hg and ²⁰⁴Tl radioisotopes, procured from the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay, were used as tracers for the distribution studies. The distribution ratio and percent extraction were determined by the usual method.

Results and Discussion

Extraction in oxygenated solvents :

The extraction behaviour of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) was studied from aqueous thiocyanate solutions into *n*-butanol, nitrobenzene and ethyl acetate (Fig. 1). Generally, the extractions are poor in nitrobenzene. The extraction of zinc(II) increases upto a thiocyanate concentration of 0.1M and thereafter becomes almost constant. On the other hand the extraction of mercury(II) decreases upto 0.1M and remains almost constant thereafter. Cadmium(II), thallium(I) and thallium(III) show negligible extraction in all the solvents.

Mercury(II) can be separated from cadmium(II), thallium(I) and thallium(III) by extracting it into *n*-butanol from $\leq 0.02M$ thiocyanate solution. Zinc(II) can be separated from cadmium(II), thallium(I) and thallium(III) by extracting into *n*-butanol or ethyl acetate at thiocyanate concentration $\geq 0.1M$.

Extraction of thiocyanate complexes of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) in HMWA :

The extraction behaviour of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) from aqueous thiocyanate solutions, as studied in chloroform and benzene solutions of

Fig. 1. Extraction of Zn(II) and Hg(II) from thiocyanate solutions by oxygenated solvents. Zn(II): x-*n*-butanol, □-ethyl acetate Hg(II): ●-*n*-butanol (equilibrated), - - -*n*-butanol (unequibrated), ○-nitrobenzene, △-ethylacetate.

Fig. 2. Extraction of Zn(II) from NH_4SCN solutions by various 0.1M amines in chloroform and benzene. Chloroform solvent: (1) Primene JM-T; (2) Amberlite LA-1; (3) Alamine 336; (4) Aliquat 336. Benzene solvent: (5) Primene JM-T; (6) Amberlite LA-1; (7) Alamine 336; (8) Aliquat 336.

Fig. 3. Extraction of Cd(II) from NH_4SCN solutions by various 0.1M amines in chloroform and benzene. Chloroform solvent: (1) Primene JM-T; (2) Amberlite LA-1; (3) Alamine 336; (4) Aliquat 336. Benzene Solvent: (5) Primene JM-T; (6) Amberlite LA-1; (7) Alamine 336; (8) Aliquat 336.

Fig. 4. Extraction of Hg(II) from NH_4SCN solutions by various 0.1M amines in chloroform and benzene. Chloroform solvent: (1) Primene JM-T; (2) Amberlite LA-1; (3) Alamine 336; (4) Aliquat 336. Benzene solvent: (5) Primene JM-T; (6) Amberlite LA-1; (7) Alamine 336; (8) Aliquat 336.

different liquid anion exchangers, is shown in Figs. 2,3 and 4, respectively. The extraction of all the three metal ions increases with decreasing thiocyanate concentration with a tendency to attain a limiting value. The effect of pH of the aqueous phase on the extractions was found to be negligible within the pH range 2.0 to 5.0. The extraction behaviour of these elements is more or less similar to their sorption on solid anion-exchange resins¹⁰. The extractive power of the various amines for all these elements follows the order:

primary < secondary $\lesssim$ tertiary < quaternary. It is also apparent from these extraction studies that the extractions with benzene as diluent are, generally, higher than those obtained with chloroform diluent. The extractions of these elements in a particular amine-diluent system are in accordance with the stability¹¹ of their respective thiocyanate complexes in aqueous solutions i.e. $\text{Cd} < \text{Zn} < \text{Hg}$.

Identification of the extracted species :

The stoichiometry of the extracted species has been determined by extraction isotherms, log-log plots of amine concentration versus distribution ratio and analysis of organic extract at maximum loading conditions. The results on extracted species are summarized in Table 1. It is apparent from the results of the various methods employed to determine the nature of the extracting species that there is a fairly good agreement between the results of loading experiments and analysis data. But in some

TABLE 1—RESULTS ON IDENTIFICATION OF EXTRACTING SPECIES IN HMWA

Metal ion	Amine	Species identified by		
		Log-log plot	Extraction isotherm	Analysis of organic extract
Zn^{2+}	Alamine 336	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_3^{2-}$	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$
	Aliquat 336	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_3^{2-}$	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$
Cd^{2+}	Aliquat 336	$\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2^-$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2^-$
Hg^{2+}	Alamine 336	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_3^{2-}$	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$
	Aliquat 336	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_3^{2-}$	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$	$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2^-$

cases the results of these two methods do not agree with those of log-log plots. This anomaly is, generally, attributed to the largely different experimental conditions existing in the two methods. In log-log plots, the metal ion concentration is extremely low ($< 10^{-6} M$) whereas a much higher concentration has been used for extraction isotherms. Besides this, varying amine concentration, and higher amine to metal ratios have been used in log-log plots. The possibility of extraction of the different species at the different experimental conditions cannot be ruled out. However, more reliance can be placed on the results of the extraction isotherms because these results are confirmed by the analysis of the organic extract at the maximum loading conditions.

Separations :

In order to explore the thiocyanate-HMWA system for some useful separations, the extraction behaviour of indium(III) and thallium(III) has also been studied under identical experimental conditions. The best conditions of separation, based on the extraction data are given in Table 2. The efficiency of the different separations is indicated by the separation coefficients listed therein. In most of the cases the metal ion from the organic phase can be stripped by washing it with water or an appropriate concentration of nitric acid.

Extraction of zinc and cadmium thiocyanate complexes in benzene in the presence of tri-n-butyl phosphate and pyridine :

The extraction of zinc(II) and cadmium(II) thiocyanate complexes was studied by tributyl phosphate (TBP) and pyridine, diluted with benzene. The effect of pH on extraction was studied at 1.0 M NH_4SCN and a fixed concentration of TBP or pyridine. In TBP, the extraction of both the metal ions is almost independent of pH within the range 3.0-6.0. However, in the case of pyridine, the extraction increases with increasing pH of the aqueous phase and the plots of pH versus log D gave straight lines with slopes close to 1 for both the metal ions. At constant concentration of TBP or pyridine the extractions of Zn(II) and Cd(II)

TABLE 2—MUTUAL BINARY SEPARATIONS OF Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), In(III) AND Tl(III) BY VARIOUS AMINES (0.1 M) IN CHLOROFORM AND BENZENE

Metal ions separated	Extractant	Molarity of NH_4SCN	Separation coefficient (β)
Zn(II) from Cd(II)	Amberlite LA-1 in chloroform	0.1	3.6×10^3
	Alamine 336 in chloroform	0.5	1.3×10^3
Hg(II) from Cd(II)	Amberlite LA-1 in chloroform	0.5	4.6×10^3
	Alamine 336 in chloroform	0.5	2.8×10^3
Zn(II) from Tl(III)	Aliquat 336 in benzene	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
	Aliquat 336 in chloroform	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
H. (II) from Tl(III)	Aliquat 336 in benzene	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
	Aliquat 336 in chloroform	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
Cd(II) from Tl(III)	Aliquat 336 in benzene	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
	Aliquat 336 in chloroform	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$
In(III) from Tl(III)	Aliquat 336 in benzene	0.1-4.0	$> 10^4$

increase with increasing concentration of thiocyanate. The plots of $\log D$ versus $\log [\text{NH}_4\text{SCN}]$ are linear with slopes around 1, thus suggesting that $[\text{M}(\text{SCN})]^+$ species are getting extracted into the organic phase. The existence of $[\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})]^+$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})]^+$ species in aqueous solutions was reported by Chiang and Hsu¹² and Hume *et al.*¹³.

The dependence of extraction on the concentration of TBP or pyridine was studied at constant NH_4SCN concentration. The log-log plots of extractant concentration versus distribution ratio gave straight lines with slope around 2 and 4 for zinc and cadmium, respectively.

On the basis of the above results, the species being extracted are inferred to be $[\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2\text{TBP}]^+$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{SCN})_2\text{py}]^+$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_4\text{TBP}]^+$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_4\text{py}]^+$. Such species should not be extracted into a non polar medium like benzene, since they are

Fig. 5. Extraction of different metals from aqueous NH_4SCN solutions by 1.0 M TBP in benzene.

charged. Therefore, it is assumed that some anion, X^- , is associated to make the species neutral and thus extractable into benzene. For pyridine system, X^- may be either OH^- or ClO_4^- but for TBP system the possibility of OH^- is ruled out because the extractions are almost independent of pH. The possibility of ClO_4^- has been suggested because it is present in larger excess in the aqueous phase as perchloric acid has been used for adjusting the pH.

Fig. 6. Extraction of different metals from aqueous NH_4SCN solutions by 0.1 M pyridine in benzene.

The extraction behaviour of silver(I), manganese(II), cobalt(II), mercury(II) and thallium(III) in addition to zinc(II) and cadmium(II) has been studied as a function of NH_4SCN concentration keeping the concentration of TBP or pyridine constant (Figs. 5 and 6). On the basis of the extraction data it has been possible to achieve some typical separations of analytical and radiochemical interest. The conditions for various separations along with

separation factors are given in Tables 3 and 4. In all the cases, metal ion from the organic phase can be conveniently stripped by washing it with distilled water.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF Zn(II) FROM Ag(I), Mn(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) AND Tl(III) FROM NH₄SCN SOLUTIONS BY TBP (1.0 M) IN BENZENE

Zn(II) separated from	Molarity of NH ₄ SCN	Separation coefficient (β)
Ag(I)	0.5	9 × 10 ³
Mn(II)	0.05	3.4 × 10 ³
Co(II)	0.1	3 × 10 ³
Cd(II)	0.05	7.2 × 10 ³
Hg(II)	0.5	5 × 10 ³
Tl(III)	0.01–1.0	> 10 ⁴

TABLE 4—SOME BINARY METAL ION SEPARATIONS FROM NH₄SCN SOLUTIONS BY PYRIDINE (0.1 M) IN BENZENE

Metal ions separated	Molarity of NH ₄ SCN	Separation coefficient (β)
Mn(II)–Co(II)	0.5	6.6 × 10 ³
Zn(II)–Hg(II)	0.5	2 × 10 ³
Zn(II)–Ag(I)	0.5	4 × 10 ³
Cd(II)–Ag(I)	0.5	2 × 10 ³
Cd(II)–Hg(II)	0.5	2 × 10 ³
Cd(II)–Tl(III)	0.1–0.5	> 10 ³

Conclusion :

The present studies on the extraction of metal ions as thiocyanate reveal that most of the metal ions investigated show negligible extraction in non-oxygenated solvents. Some of the metal ions are extracted by oxygenated solvents but the extractions, in general, are not quantitative. High molecular weight amines are better extractants for Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and In(III) from aqueous thiocyanate

solutions. These amine extraction systems are more useful for the separations and provide conditions for metal ion separations like Zn(II)-Cd(II), Cd(II)-Hg(II), Cd(II)-Tl(III), Hg(II)-Tl(III) and In(III)-Tl(III) (Table 2) with high separation factors. The tributyl phosphate system is only useful for the separation of Zn(II) from other metal ions, while the pyridine thiocyanate system is more versatile and offers conditions for a variety of binary metal ion separations, viz., Mn(II)-Co(II), Zn(II)-Hg(II), Zn(II)-Ag(I), Cd(II)-Ag(I), Cd(II)-Hg(II) and Cd(II)-Tl(III). To conclude, the thiocyanate-HMWA systems are more versatile and generally provide separations with higher separation factors.

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